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Executive summary

The objective of this report is to propose initiatives for unified repositories providing processed human gut microbiome data, a crucial endeavour for advancing research in this field. The report leverages the work done on Milestone MS13 (*“Unified repositories and resources for microbiome summary data”*) that surveyed and reported publicly available resources that consistently provide processed summary data from microbiome samples. Fundamentals for these resources were to be based on data types we previously identified in MS08 (*“Review on major microbiomics data types”*) and analysis types identified in MS09 (*“List of recommended essential microbiome analysis types for primary and secondary analysis”*). Publicly available resources, repositories, and databases can promote standardization in the field by providing the research community with processed data analyzed using standardized methods that are more similar to the data used by researchers in their work. This will promote both data types and analysis methods that were initially adopted by the aforementioned resources and repositories. Moreover, such repositories can significantly improve data accessibility, reproducibility, and collaboration.

Report proposing initiatives for unified repositories for processed data

In this report, we address the need to establish unified repositories for processed human gut microbiome data, presenting a framework of initiatives and minimum requirements that are crucial for their implementation and development.

The microbiome is a complex ecosystem of trillions of microorganisms inhabiting a specific ecological niche and is a subject of increasing scientific interest due to many research works showing its profound influence on human health. It has been widely shown in the scientific literature that the human gut microbiome plays a pivotal role in human health, influencing various physiological processes and disease states. Research in this field has unveiled the microbiome's role in nutrition, immune function, the aetiology of various diseases including cancer, metabolic disorders, inflammatory conditions, and the response to therapies.

The continuous generation of publicly available microbiome data by research studies in recent years has brought new challenges in the field related to data accessibility, standardization, and reproducibility of results. Researchers currently face hurdles due to the lack of repositories providing standardized microbiome data that hinder data access and their re-usability for validation of published results. This is most critical as data from large cohorts keeps emerging and recent initiatives anticipate the analysis of hundreds of thousands of samples.

This report outlines key initiatives encompassing data submission, standardization, quality control, data storage, metadata, and version tracking. To overcome these challenges, this report seeks to propose a set of minimum standards that can unify repositories that provide processed human gut microbiome data. The primary goal is to streamline data sharing, improve data quality, and foster a collaborative environment within the microbiome research community.

Implementing these initiatives aims to facilitate collaborations, streamline research and allow much easier data integration and validation, primarily focusing on the human microbiome field, but not only limited to that if employed by other microbiome research scientists. These repositories will serve as invaluable resources, enhancing the rigour and reproducibility of studies in the field and expediting the translation of microbiome insights into innovative therapies and personalized medicine. All these issues hinder scientific progress and the translation of results from microbiome research into clinical and industrial applications. The initiatives put forth in this report represent a significant step toward realizing the full potential of human gut microbiome research and its profound implications for human health and disease.

The report submitted with the Milestone MS13 (*“Unified repositories and resources for microbiome summary data”*) had the objective of surveying both repositories and resources providing summary microbiome data. The report identified 12 different resources. Some of them provide online platforms for data analysis while others only provide raw microbiome data that can be downloaded and re-analyzed. Of those that are providing processed microbiome data, the common characteristics reported appear to be the geographical origin where the microbiome samples were collected, the age and sex of the individual at collection time, and the sequencing biotechnological framework employed to generate the raw microbiome data. These information are important when using publicly available samples as validation for the researcher’s analysis, so it is possible to account for the potential biases due to the use of different sequencing platforms to generate the metagenomic data, as well as the effect of age and sex on the microbiome composition. However, with these limited samples and individuals’ information, only limited comparative or meta-analyses can be performed. In particular, in the endeavour to seek robust results validation, it is important to have public access to external independent cohorts that span over more than one country and that detail the same samples or individuals’ information that the researchers seek to validate. In particular, researchers should put effort into the rigorous documentation to report the procedures used for sample collection and nucleic acid extraction, as these are also potential sources of bias.

The analysis of the repositories and resources providing summary microbiome data gave us the possibility to identify some examples of 'good practices' that could lead to the specification of unified repositories. Examples are curatedMetagenomicData and Qiita. The former because it models most of the information available when generating human microbiome samples and allows conducting meta-analysis correcting for all major biases known to impact microbiome composition. The latter, Qiita, instead is a platform that also allows to perform analysis and allow to keep track of the pipeline of analysis that generated a specific result. Both these aspects are very important towards the FAIR principles, in particular, for proper interoperability, reusability, and results validation.

Making data and data-related information publicly available is also raising concerns in Europe about potential infringement of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) privacy law. Although we can identify a minimum set of information that should be collected and provided in addition to the raw or processed microbiome data, it is important to define at a more global level how microbiome data, samples and individuals’ information can be safely made publicly available. This is a very important aspect to allow the researchers in the field to access, re-analyze, and integrate this public data into their study. Repositories and resources that provide processed microbiome data represent a significant step toward overcoming obstacles in scientific progress and practical applications and fully unlocking the potential of human gut microbiome research for human health and disease.